

CONSTRAINTS AND SUGGESTIONS FACED BY THE CLUSTER FRONT LINE DEMONSTRATIONS (CFLDs)
BENEFICIARY FARMERS IN CHITTOOR DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract:

Cluster Front Line Demonstrations (CFLDs) are a significant extension approach in the field of agriculture, particularly in India. They are organized by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) and various state agricultural universities. CFLDs play a crucial role in disseminating cutting-edge agricultural technologies, fostering innovation, and promoting sustainable farming practices among Indian farmers. The present study was conducted in Chittoor district of Andhra Pradesh to understand the CFLDs beneficiary farmers constraints while availing their services and suggestions to overcome them. The data was collected from the beneficiary farmers under two KVKs selected villages. Simple random sampling technique, purposive sampling and descriptive research design was used for the purpose of the study. By using Garrett ranking method it was found that the major problems faced was regarding insufficient quantity of seed of new variety given under CFLDs (I), difficult to maintain purity of seed due to low quantity of seed input(II). Most of them suggested that Demonstration should be repeated regularly (I), low cost technology needs to be introduced (II).

Keywords - Cluster Front Line, Farmer, Chittoor district.

Introduction:

Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVKs), a frontline extension system at the district level, plays a vital role in evaluating and refining agricultural technologies. It conducts large-scale demonstrations of successful technologies to persuade farmers to adopt them, thereby increasing their usage. To boost oilseed crop production and productivity in India, the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare, Government of India, initiated the "Cluster Frontline Demonstrations of Oilseeds in 2017-18" project under the National Mission on Oilseeds and Oil Palm (NMOOP). This project was implemented through eleven ICAR-Agricultural Technology Application Research Institutes (ATARI) across the country.

Cluster Frontline Demonstrations (CFLDs) hold immense significance in agricultural development and innovation adoption. They serve as practical platforms to showcase and promote new agricultural practices, technologies, and techniques to farmers. By bridging the gap between research institutions and farmers, CFLDs facilitate the transfer of knowledge, leading to improved agricultural productivity and enhanced livelihoods for farmers. Cluster frontline demonstrations are conducted in specific geographic clusters, where groups of farmers collectively participate in demonstrating innovative agricultural practices. These demonstrations are usually organized by agricultural extension agencies, research institutions, or non-governmental organizations in collaboration with local farmers' groups or cooperatives. The primary aim of these demonstrations is to provide farmers with firsthand experience, demonstrating the benefits and effectiveness of adopting new agricultural technologies and practices. With this context, the present study was undertaken to have a critical understanding of the Cluster Front Line Demonstration (CFLDs) beneficiary farmers in Chittoor district of Andhra Pradesh with the following objectives:

i. To study the constraints and suggestions with respect to effective implementation of Cluster Front Line Demonstrations (CFLDs) beneficiary farmer's

Methodology

For this study, Chittoor district in Andhra Pradesh was purposively selected due to the researcher's familiarity with the district as a native. This familiarity facilitated a comprehensive investigation through personal observations, taking into account the social conditions, local language, cultural aspects, and interactions with relevant personnel such as officers and KVK scientists. Specifically, Krishi Vigyan

Kendra in Kalikiri and Rashtriya Seva Samithi - Krishi Vigyan Kendra (RASS-KVK) in Karakambadi, both located in Chittoor district, were purposively selected for the study. Two mandals adopted by each KVK were also selected purposively. Within each selected mandal, three villages were selected using a purposive sampling technique, resulting in a total of six villages. To ensure a representative sample, 10 CFLDs beneficiary farmers and 10 non-beneficiary farmers were randomly selected from each of the chosen villages, totaling 120 respondents. Primary data was collected with the help of a well-structured and pre-tested interview schedule and the requisite secondary data was collected from various Government offices like KVK scientists, journals, magazines, publications etc.

Analytical tool

The problems experienced by the CFLDs beneficiary farmers and suggestions to overcome in availing of the services were analysed. Descriptive statistics like Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard deviation were used for analysing the data and dividing the respondents into categories of awareness. Constraints while adopting Cluster Front Line demonstrations and suggestions to improve them were identified in consultation with village leaders and progressive farmers and respondents were asked to rank the problems and suggestions. Garrett's Ranking Technique provides the change of orders of constraints and advantages into numerical scores. The notable superiority of this technique over simple frequency distribution is that the constraints are arranged based on their intensity from the point of view of respondents. Garrett's formula for converting ranks into percent is:

$$\text{Percent position} = 100 * (R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$$

Where,

R_{ij} = rank given for i^{th} constraint by j^{th} individual,

N_j = number of constraint ranked by j^{th} individual.

The per cent position of each rank is converted into scores referring to the table given by Garrett and Woodworth (1969). For each factor, the scores of individual respondents were added together and divided by the total number of the respondents for whom scores will be added. These mean scores for all the constraints and suggestion were arranged in descending order and the constraints and suggestions were accordingly ranked.

Results and Discussion

Constraints Faced by CFLDs Beneficiary Farmers

A list of constraints faced by CFLDs beneficiary farmers were presented in the following Table 1 and Figure 1.

Regarding constraints expressed by CFLDs beneficiary farmers insufficient quantity of seed of new variety given under CFLDs (GS:82) was the major constraint faced by majority of beneficiary farmers and ranked first, followed by difficult to maintain purity of seed due to low quantity of seed input (GS:70) ranked second, marketing problem with new variety (GS:63) ranked third, institutional support for buy back of the produce should be arranged (GS:58) fourth, lack of proper monitoring and follow up (GS:53)

Table 1. Constraints faced by CFLDs beneficiary farmers

S. No.	Constraints	Mean Garrett Score	Rank
1.	Insufficient quantity of seed of new variety given under CFLDs	82	I
2.	Lack of proper monitoring and follow up	53	V
3.	Marketing problem with new variety	63	III
4.	Seed multiplication by each farmer is a problem due to meagre area under CFLDs	47	VI
5.	Unavailability of sufficient labour in time	37	VIII
6.	Institutional support for buy back of the produce should be arranged	58	IV
7.	Insufficient quantity of fertilizers and pesticides	42	VII
8.	Difficult to maintain purity of seed due to low quantity of seed input	70	II
9.	Unable to maintain seed continuity due to cultivation of the new variety once in a year	30	IX
10.	Low yield due to adverse climatic conditions	18	X

fifth, seed multiplication by each farmer is a problem due to meagre area under CFLDs (GS:47) sixth, insufficient quantity of fertilizers and pesticides (GS:42) seventh, unavailability of sufficient labour in time (GS:37) eighth, unable to maintain seed continuity due to cultivation of the new variety once in a year (GS:30) ninth and low yield due to adverse climatic conditions (GS:18) tenth. These findings were similar with the findings of Deshmukh et al. (2018), Raghuwanshi et al. (2018), Sisodiya et al.(2018) and Anuratha et al. (2019).

Figure 1. Constraints faced by CFLDs beneficiary farmers.

‘Insufficient quantity of seed of new variety given under CFLDs’ was expressed as prime constraint by majority (88.33%) of CFLDs beneficiary farmers. The aim of CFLDs was to establish production potential of technologies under farmers fields. As per the operational guidelines of CFLDs the maximum area under demonstration was 0.4 ha, but due to higher cost of seed which is supplied to beneficiaries as input, seed was supplied only to 0.1 ha.

Difficult to maintain purity of seed due to low quantity of seed input’ was expressed as second constraint by the CFLDs beneficiary farmers (GS: 82). Because the quantity of seed provided to farmers is low which is sufficient for 0.1 acre, they are unable to grow it over a vast region, and the purity of the seed may be lost if farmers mix different varieties of seed and grow in their fields. On the other hand the output from the demonstrated area was nominal so it was difficult to maintain seed purity without mixing with other varieties.

‘Marketing problem with new variety’ was the third constraint expressed by (GS:70) of the CFLDs beneficiary farmers. Farmers were facing marketing issues since a new type of variety may not be accepted in some markets, and farmers may not be able to obtain the maximum price for the new variety. Because the vast majority of them are still using the ruling old variety.

‘Institutional support for buy back of the produce should be arranged’ was expressed as fourth constraint by (GS: 63) of CFLDs beneficiary

farmers. Farmers would not be able to sell the new variety of seed in the market right away, and if they do, they will not be able to obtain higher and immediate returns to their produce. As a result, KVKs should set up a buy-back seed programme allowing farmers to receive immediate returns.

‘Lack of proper monitoring and follow up’ was expressed as fifth constraint by (GS: 58) of CFLDs beneficiary farmers. Farmers felt that there is a lack of monitoring by the scientists when they need suggestions to their problems in their fields about new technology.

‘Seed multiplication by each farmer is a problem due to meagre area under CFLDs’ was expressed as sixth constraint by (GS: 53) of CFLDs beneficiary farmers. Only 0.1 ha was cultivated under CFLDs by the farmers so it was very difficult for the seed multiplication.

‘Insufficient quantity of fertilizers and pesticides’ was expressed as seventh constraint by (GS:42) of CFLDs beneficiary farmers. Farmers felt that fertilizers and pesticides provided by the KVK under CFLDs was not sufficient to their fields. Probable it was due to limited budget under CFLDs that KVKs might have not supplied all inputs in adequate quantity.

‘Unavailability of sufficient labour in time’ was the next constraint expressed by (GS:37) of CFLDs beneficiary farmers. The availability of the labour was very difficult at the peak period and there will be much demand to the labour.

'Unable to maintain seed continuity due to cultivation of the new variety once in a year' was expressed as the ninth constraint by (GS: 30) of CFLDs beneficiary farmers. It was probably due to cultivation of groundnut crop once a year under rainfed conditions and it was difficult to maintain the quality of seed for one year.

'Low yield due to adverse climatic conditions' was expressed as the tenth constraint by (GS:18) of CFLDs beneficiary farmers. Because the variety given under CFLDs may be good but due to adverse climatic conditions the variety might not have yielded up to its potential and gave the unexpected result.

Suggestions Given by CFLDs Beneficiary Farmers to Overcome the Constraints

List of suggestions given by CFLDs beneficiary farmers to overcome the constraints were presented in the following Table 2 and Figure 2. The findings of the table 4.35 point out that among all suggestions given by CFLDs beneficiary farmers, Demonstration should be

repeated regularly (91.67%) was one of the major suggestion and ranked first, followed by low cost technology needs to be introduced (88.33%) ranked second, KVKs should arrange a buyback of seed to get immediate returns to the farmer (83.33%) ranked third, timely visit by extension personnel and specialist should be carrying on for guidance (80.00%) ranked fourth, follow up with beneficiaries needs to be carried out after completion of demonstrations (75.00%) ranked fifth, fertilizer and pesticides must be provided under CFLDs for timely application (73.33%) ranked sixth, fair price should be given to the produce of CFLDs (66.67%) ranked seventh and field day should be conducted at regular intervals (58.33%) ranked eighth. These findings were inline with the findings of Patoliya (2013), Padiyar (2017) and Gamit et al. (2018).

S. No.	Suggestions	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
1.	Demonstration should be repeated regularly	55	91.67	1
2.	Low cost technology needs to be introduced	53	88.33	2
3.	KVKs should arrange a buyback of seed to get immediate returns to the farmers	50	83.33	3
4.	KVK scientists should visit farmers fields on a frequent basis	48	80.00	4
5.	Follow up with beneficiaries needs to be carried out after the completion of demonstrations	45	75.00	5
6.	Fertilizers and pesticides must be provided under CFLDs for timely application	44	73.33	6
7.	Fair price should be given to the produce of CFLDs	40	66.67	7
8.	Field day should be conducted at regular intervals	35	58.33	8

Figure 2. Suggestions given by CFLDs beneficiary farmers.

Majority of the CFLDs beneficiary farmers suggested that demonstration should be repeated regularly to get familiarize with concept of CFLDs, new varieties and technologies disseminated by KVK under CFLDs where the farmers face difficult to understand.

Next suggestion that majority of CFLDs beneficiary farmers felt that low cost technology needs to be introduced because majority of farmers are small farmers and cannot afford if the technology cost expensive.

Next suggestion of CFLDs beneficiary farmers was KVKs should arrange a buyback of seed to get immediate returns to the farmers because farmers are unable to sell new variety in the market and cannot get more price to their produce.

The next valuable suggestion of CFLDs beneficiary farmers was timely visit by extension personnel and specialist should be carrying on for guidance. Most of the farmers felt that if there is any problem

in the field they cannot get solutions to that problem, so timely visit of extension personnel and specialists help them to get solutions to that problem.

Next suggestion was follow up with beneficiaries needs to be carried out after the completion of demonstrations, because it helps the farmers to have regular interaction with scientists of KVK about new technologies.

The next valuable suggestion of CFLDs beneficiary farmers was fertilizers and pesticides must be provided under CFLDs for timely application which could improve the productivity and production of crop, ultimately increases the net returns of the crop.

Next suggestion given by the CFLDs beneficiary farmers was Fair price should be given to the product by KVK, by utilizing this year CFLDs seed for next year CFLDs through buying the seed from beneficiaries by paying fair price to their product.

CFLDs beneficiary farmers suggested to conduct field day with large number of farmers by showing its distinct features of new variety than the local variety.

Conclusion:

From this study it can be concluded, that major constraints faced by the farmers, top constraints were problems regarding insufficient quantity of seed of new variety given under CFLDs, difficult to maintain purity of seed due to low quantity of seed input and marketing problem with new variety. It was found that the least perceived constraint was low yield due to adverse climatic conditions. It was reported in the present study that the beneficiary farmers had some suggestions regarding the Cluster Front Line Demonstrations and they are demonstration should be repeated regularly, low cost technology needs to be introduced and KVKs should arrange a buyback of seed to get immediate returns to the farmer. Overall, from this research it is evident that providing beneficiary farmers with Certified Foundation Seed with adequate quantity can significantly enhance their crop yield. Furthermore, regular repetition of technology demonstrations by KVKs is crucial for improving farmers' knowledge and ensuring affordability of low-cost technologies. These measures collectively contribute to the improvement of farmers' livelihoods and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

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